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Constitutional Patriotism as Europe's Public Philosophy? On the Responsiveness of Post-National Law

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Abstract:

This paper scrutinizes Jürgen Habermas's concept of constitutional patriotism—and its basis in his discourse theory of democracy and law—as the substance of a European public philosophy. Drawing on critical theorists' reception of the concept and Habermas's own contemporary writings on Europe's crisis, I reconstruct constitutional patriotism from the analytic perspective of 'constitutional imaginaries'. A constitutional imaginary emphasizes the relation of law to the broader societal and political meanings that create and interpret it from outside formal legal institutions. This perspective 'thickens' our understanding of the meaning of law as an object of public commitment, as well as of the processes through which this meaning changes (constitutional politics). The paper then details the consequences of this shift for the work of the contemporary European judiciary and its constitutional discourse. In the first instance, analysis of constitutional imaginaries reveals the extent to which civic attachment to constitutional law is oriented not merely to a legal principle simpliciter but also to the historical settlement of political conflict the principle reflects. This suggests that the plurality of constitutional imaginaries in the European legal space creates additional difficulties for inspiring civic attachments post-nationally, a problem to which European judiciaries have heretofore been unresponsive. Second, an understanding of Habermas's work in light of constitutional imaginaries opens new avenues for rethinking the interpretive and structural tasks to which Europe's juridical institutions should be directed. In particular, the chapter highlights new forms of proceduralism to be recovered in constitutional discourse in order to establish a reflexivity of constitutional imagination adequate to post-national politics.^a

KEYWORDS: constitutional patriotism, European Union, constitutional imaginary, solidarity, proceduralism, imagination

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Paul Linden-Retek*

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Paul Linden-Retek*

'Law is the place from which we begin the struggle for and against identity.'
Paul Kahn, *Law and Love: The Trials of King Lear*

I. INTRODUCTION: POST-NATIONALITY AND LAW

More than a generation ago, Jürgen Habermas put forward his theory of 'constitutional patriotism' to sustain a constellation of politics, law, and identity beyond the national-state.¹ It is worth evaluating where the concept leaves us today. The European Union's present crises reveal, regrettably, that post-national political commitment oriented to the precepts of legal principle is awfully fragile. Indeed, Europe's foundational commitments enumerated in Article 2 TEU to democracy, human rights, and the rule of law—precisely the values to which a constitutional patriot adheres—are the subjects of profound crisis, hypocrisy, disagreement, and disregard: the plight of refugees at Europe's shores; the machinations and uncertainties of Brexit; burgeoning 'illiberal democracy' in the East; and undemocratic 'authoritarian liberalism' in Brussels. These challenges question the adequacy of constitutional patriotism as Europe's public philosophy.

This chapter scrutinizes Habermas's concept—and its basis in his discourse theory of democracy and law—to seek a constructive critique. I read constitutional patriotism in light of critical theorists' reception of the concept and Habermas's own contemporary writings on Europe's crisis. This investigation yields a necessary corrective shift in analytical perspective: the frame of constitutional imaginaries. The chapter then details the consequences of this shift for the work of the contemporary European judiciary and its constitutional discourse.

The idea of constitutional imaginary emphasizes the connection between law's legitimacy and its broader 'social imaginary': the process by which law draws from or makes a claim to the orientations, practices, and values in citizens' lifeworlds beyond law's formal instruments. This connection is dynamic and dialectical, as both law and society are changed by it—but they are not always changed equally, in the same measure, or in the same sense. And this means that law's responsiveness to social imagination complicates the nature of constitutional patriotism's central object: legal principle. It thus accordingly complicates the nature of civic attachment to it, as well.

When citizens affirm legal principles, they implicitly affirm certain settlements to political conflict. These settlements have a particularized character, embedded within the ongoing struggles for redistribution and recognition in a democratic community. These struggles are given meaning, in the first instance, by the articulations of national democracy. Attachment to principles that are formally identical can be motivated, across jurisdictions and polities, by quite distinct political affects and commitments, which may or may not themselves neatly align in the post-national political sphere. European constitutional patriotism thereby always confronts the possibility of significant disjunctions in the public meaning of the law, to which it seeks allegiance. At moments of heightened disagreement, this problem can lead to a general collapse of legitimacy and faith in the post-national rule of law.

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¹ See Jürgen Habermas, 'Political Culture in Germany since 1968' in *The New Conservatism: Cultural Criticism and the Historians' Debate* (SW Nichol森 ed and trans, Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 1989); Jürgen Habermas, 'Citizenship and National Identity: Some Reflections on the Future of Europe' in Ronald Beiner (ed), *Theorizing Citizenship* (Albany: State University of New York Press 1995) 255; Jürgen Habermas, 'Remarks on Dieter Grimm's "Does Europe Need a Constitution?"' (1995) 1(3) *European Law Journal* 303; Jürgen Habermas, *The Inclusion of the Other: Studies in Political Theory* (C. Cronin and P de Greiff eds, Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 1998); Jürgen Habermas, *The Postnational Constellation: Political Essays* (Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 2001).

The salient question to answer is not, as Habermas's early formulations of constitutional patriotism supposed, the extent to which universal constitutional principles—and the formal-procedural presuppositions behind them—should be the source of post-national constitutional commitments. Emphasis ought instead be placed on how constitutional imaginaries function at once as normative resources for but also ideological limits of the post-national creativity of European law.

If this is correct, this account helps illuminate why constitutional patriotism is increasingly strained as a post-national public philosophy. In the first instance, post-national constitutional law must be responsive to the way existing legal doctrines neglect the force of constitutional imaginaries. This challenges a core jurisprudential tenet of the European Court of Justice, on which the 'integration through law' project has heretofore been founded: the autonomy and effectiveness of the European regulatory order. Insofar as it remains inattentive to constitutional imagination, such autonomy—if it might have once served a particular integrative purpose—today serves to hinder, not support, the creation of post-national identity and commitment. I demonstrate this point below with reference to an issue of utmost real and symbolic importance to post-national political commitments: the highly fraught development of a fair and robust European system of asylum protections.

In turn, I advise a reformed conception of constitutional patriotism grounded in responsiveness to constitutional imaginaries, which poses positive demands on European law. It suggests that true responsiveness would entail distinct modes of argumentation and interpretation: historical analysis, cross-jurisdictional translation, and material political consciousness, among them. While such interpretation is of course demanding, it is the only way in which judicial interpretation can sustain legal principles as both objects of post-national commitment and objects of national meaning.

II. CONSTITUTIONAL PATRIOTISM AND SOLIDARITY BEYOND THE NATION-STATE

The development of constitutional patriotism spans Habermas's early writings on post-war German political identity to his related, subsequent efforts to ground a European political culture beyond the nation-state.² Habermas acknowledges that a legal system of rights protection 'must be enduringly linked with the motivations and convictions of the citizens, for without such a motivational anchoring they could not become the driving force behind the dynamically conceived project of producing an association of [free and equal] individuals'.³ Yet, Habermas also maintains that any theories that derive such anchoring from the 'ambivalent bonding force of archaic institutions' are wedded to the now utterly discredited 'metasocial guarantees of the sacred'.⁴ Constitutional patriotism—as the form of motivational affect directed towards constitutional principles themselves—supersedes the particularist tendencies of pre-political ethnic-nationalist recognition, attaching instead (ultimately) to universalist rights and norms embedded in constitutional law.⁵ Constitutional patriotism offers a procedural basis for social cohesion within a post-metaphysical, pluralistic polity.

On this reading, solidarity is one of 'the results or the "product" of constitutional patriotism': in Habermas's definition, 'an abstract, legally mediated solidarity between strangers'.⁶ It is tied to the success and vitality of reasoning among citizens in the public sphere, secured by the co-original implication of private and public autonomy, by both liberal and republican participatory rights.⁷ Over time, this relationship of mutual and reciprocal participation assumes among citizens the structure of a shared constitutional project that exceeds the boundaries of national states and parochial political communities. The premise is that constitutional patriotism can link together national communities without requiring or presuming an already formed and fully-consolidated transnational demos, one that would make the ongoing work and negotiation of the terms of solidarity superfluous.

Constitutional patriotism imagines a 'transformative conception of living together'.⁸ It shifts the understanding of political identity from the 'unreflective' identification with particular national traditions to 'dynamic and complex processes of identity-formation'.⁹ 'What matters', Jan-Werner Müller writes, 'is a kind of critical, highly self-conscious back-and-forth between actually existing traditions and institutions, on the one hand, and the best universal norms and

2 See generally Jan-Werner Müller, *Constitutional Patriotism* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 2007).

3 Jürgen Habermas, 'Struggles for Recognition in the Democratic Constitutional State' in A Guttman (ed) *Multiculturalism* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 1994) 134.

4 Jürgen Habermas, *Between Facts and Norms: Contributions to a Discourse Theory of Law and Democracy* (William Rehg tr, Cambridge, MA: The Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 1998 [1992]) 27.

5 See Jürgen Habermas, *The New Conservatism* (n 1). See also Charles Maier, *The Unmasterable Past: History, Holocaust, and German National Identity* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press 1988); D Sternberger, 'Verfassungspatriotismus', *Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung*, 23 May 1979.

6 Jan-Werner Müller, *Constitutional Patriotism* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 2007) 63; Jürgen Habermas, 'Why Europe Needs a Constitution' (2001) 11 *New Left Review* 5, 16.

7 See generally Habermas, *Between Facts and Norms* (n 4) 104.

8 Müller, *Constitutional Patriotism* (n 2) 71.

9 *ibid* 29, emphasis mine.

ideas that can be worked out, on the other'.¹⁰ Constitutional patriotism is a 'collective learning process', in which 'citizens see their constitutional culture as always *open* and *incomplete*'.¹¹

Left implicit but very much central to preserving post-national solidarity under constitutional patriotism is the idea that there is a 'life of the law'. Habermas, in elegant and powerful prose, embraces this spirit: '[T]he constitutional state does not represent a finished structure but a delicate and sensitive—above all fallible and revisable—enterprise, whose purpose it to realize rights *anew* in changing circumstances, that is, to interpret the system of rights better, to institutionalize it more appropriately, and to draw out its contents more radically'.¹² This is perhaps the crucial hope of constitutional patriotism in the post-national context. If constitutional law can indeed be considered open in this fundamental sense, then competing polities might meaningfully intertwine their constitutional claims so as to support the kind of cross-border solidaristic commitments needed today. However, much hinges on how such processes of open-ended identity-formation are meant to proceed vis-à-vis constitutional legal process.

A salient structural tension within constitutional patriotism is between universal norms in constitutional law and the particular ways they are interpreted, contextualized, and embedded in constitutional practice. The tension endures because it remains unclear in Habermas's theory whether the real constitutional attachments capable of sustaining public trust are to the principles or to the particular character of the social worlds that give principles their specific meanings. The post-national possibilities of solidarity—precisely as the product of this attachment—very much depend on the objects of attachment we have in mind.

Habermas writes in a crucial, but ambiguous passage that '[s]olidarity ... arises out of law only indirectly, of course: by *stabilizing* behavioral expectations, law simultaneously secures symmetrical relationships of reciprocal recognition between abstract bearers of individual rights'.¹³ Such stabilization involves not merely abstract rights as elements of a democratic procedural consensus but also an understanding of the meaning of these rights as citizens live and invoke them in political practice. It thereby remains somehow related, if not entirely wedded or reduced, to certain communitarian dimensions of political life.

Indeed, after criticism of constitutional patriotism's thinness, Habermas modulated the relationship he envisioned constitutional patriotism to establish between universal principles of communicative rationality and a particular political-cultural tradition. No longer a direct attachment to universal principles *simpliciter*, constitutional patriotism in this new light now signified a more particularized and historicized attachment: to 'the political order and the principles of the [German] Basic Law'.¹⁴ While Habermas has not completely left behind his previous abstract formulations, he now immediately situates references to constitutional patriotism 'within the historical context of a legal community'¹⁵ or simply a 'shared political culture'.¹⁶ The principles in positive law must be given, as Habermas admits, a definite shape. He writes: 'The identity of a person, of a group, of a nation, or of a region is always something concrete, something particular'; it cannot 'consist merely in general moral orientations and characteristics, which are shared by all alike' but must instead present an 'image' to oneself and others.¹⁷ To suture commitment to legal procedures, Habermas invokes a fixed, specified image of a people that is (at least for a time) unified and bounded. The object of attachment, the means by which citizens feel bound and committed to the law and to one another, is now this stabilization of expectations in light of a political culture of law that is historically and culturally specific.

If constitutional patriotism is to remain a source of solidarity that does not foreclose the universalizing character of law, however, this relationship to political culture must have rather distinct characteristics. While Habermas rules out the particularity of an ethnic or linguistic-cultural grounding for political commitment, a different sort of particularism does indeed underwrite the embrace of constitutional principles. The nature of the 'shared political culture' must be dissociated from a 'hegemonic majority culture' and 'uncoupled from the level of subcultures and their prepolitical identities', such that 'different cultural, ethnic, and religious forms of life [can] 'interact on equal terms within *the same* political community'.¹⁸ This is what Habermas has in mind when he reiterates that, in post-conventional societies, 'republicanism must learn to stand on its own feet'.¹⁹ Thus, while solidarity grounds itself in particular allegiances to different constitutions with different interpretations of the catalogue of rights, such allegiance still engenders a consciousness of the universal. In the post-national context, 'the *same* legal principles would ... have to be interpreted

10 *ibid.*

11 *ibid.* 61.

12 Habermas, *Between Facts and Norms* (n 4) 384.

13 *ibid.* 448-9, emphasis mine.

14 Jürgen Habermas, 'Historical Consciousness and Post-Traditional Identity' in *The New Conservatism* (n 1) 257.

15 Habermas, 'Struggles for Recognition in the Democratic Constitutional State' (n 3) 225.

16 Habermas, 'Citizenship and National Identity' (n 1) 264.

17 Jürgen Habermas, 'The Limits of Neo-Historicism' in *Autonomy and Solidarity: Interviews with Jürgen Habermas* (P Dews ed, London: Verso 1996) 239. See also Patchen Markell, 'Making Affect Safe for Democracy? On "Constitutional Patriotism"' (2000) 28(1) *Political Theory* 39, 50ff.

18 Jürgen Habermas, 'The European Nation-State: On the Past and Future of Sovereignty and Citizenship' in *The Inclusion of the Other* (n 1) 117-8.

19 *ibid.* 117.

from the perspectives of different national traditions and histories'²⁰ and brought into focus as part of a now transnational legal culture.

These formulations render unclear, however, what a 'shared political culture' is then left to include. What role is it meant to play in relation to law's rational discursive practices, on the one hand, and the broader cultural meanings of the lifeworld, on the other? Consider, for example, what Habermas has said specifically about the future of a European public sphere and a supranational political culture: '[To date] by and large, the national public spheres are culturally isolated from one another. They are anchored in contexts in which political issues gain relevance only against the background of national histories and national experiences. In the future, however, differentiation could occur in a European culture between a common *political* culture and the branching *national* traditions of art and literature, historiography, philosophy, and so forth'.²¹

This construction is curious. First, Habermas accepts an analytic bifurcation of politics and culture, and ostensibly of constitutional principles and their broader social instantiations in practical experience. If this is so, it is unclear how citizens are to live out the common political culture and perceive it at once as normatively valid and socially meaningful. This risks, again, conceiving of political commitment too 'thinly'. Conversely, if we accept *some* kind of interrelationship between the thematization of political issues and their exploration in the broader cultural lifeworld, then the difference between the two scenarios Habermas identifies seems, in fact, to be minimal. As long as national cultural traditions remain 'branched' in this way, then it seems likely that the vocabularies and languages used in the public sphere will be 'culturally isolated' in the same manner, thus reducing the second scenario to the first.

There are thus two currents of thought circulating beneath Habermas's post-national constitutional project, and they flow exactly against one another. Habermas certainly wishes for a kind of political culture that nests the particular historical experiences of nations in a certain manner within the universality of democratic principles. But in the examples and elaborations Habermas has offered, the idea of a 'shared political culture' masks key contradictions in the substrate of post-national attachment. While Habermas is careful, on the one hand, to avoid making a national political culture *too* particular (embedded too firmly in cultural social groupings), he perceives the particularisms of national constitutions and their historical interpretations of rights 'more benignly', as Robert Post and Reva Siegel put it.²² While the former threatens universal democratic principles and thereby requires uncoupling, the latter comfortably gives them concrete meaning without compromising their emancipatory orientation 'one iota'.²³

But this distinction is difficult to defend without elaborating a theory precisely of constitutional culture itself. The project of post-national solidarity otherwise runs into an impasse: if the nesting of political culture within lifeworld subcultures conceals the influence of hegemonic majority cultures, then why does the same danger not attend law internationally, such that post-national solidarity is compromised from the outset by a hegemony of particular constitutional interpretations over others?²⁴ And, further, is there not conversely a sense in which we might understand the relationship between political culture and the lifeworld to be in fact necessary for constitutional patriotism, not just as a motivational reservoir but as *constitutive* of law's normativity?²⁵ Habermas seems to admit as much when he concludes: '[R]egardless of the diversity of different cultural forms of life, [democratic citizenship] does require that every citizen be *socialized* into a common political culture'.²⁶ But this is a paradoxical admission, for the influence of socialization seems to thoroughly threaten Habermas's notion of political autonomy.

III. THE SALIENCE OF CONSTITUTIONAL IMAGINARIES

Solidarity is at the heart of this dilemma. Remember that solidarity under constitutional patriotism in fact depends upon this work of nesting universal rights in particular interpretations. Solidarity must aim for the law to thicken. It must be the case that a community's political culture rests on *some* normative relationship with inherited values and traditions, inherited in the sense that they are not determined politically by the community in that present instance.²⁷ Otherwise, it is not at all clear what kinds of 'stabilized' political expectations could arise under the heading of symmetrical relations.²⁸ Solidarity would be meaningless if all were up for grabs at all times.

20 Jürgen Habermas, 'Citizenship and National Identity' in *Between Facts and Norms* (n 4) 500.

21 *ibid* 271.

22 Robert Post and Reva Siegel, 'Constitutional Patriotism and Constitutional Culture', draft on file with author, 12.

23 Habermas, 'Citizenship and National Identity' (n 20) 500.

24 See Post and Siegel, 'Constitutional Patriotism and Constitutional Culture' (n 22) 13.

25 See *ibid*; Craig Calhoun, 'Imagining Solidarity: Cosmopolitanism, Constitutional Patriotism, and the Public Sphere' (2002) 14(1) *Public Culture* 147, 152-5.

26 Habermas, 'Citizenship and National Identity' (n 20) 500, emphasis mine.

27 See Markell, 'Making Affect Safe for Democracy?' (n 17) 52.

28 See Ferrara, 'Of Boats and Principles: Reflections on Habermas's "Constitutional Democracy"' (2001) 29(6) *Political Theory* 788.

In his lucid account of the concept, Frank Michelman draws special attention to this stabilizing ‘core’ of communal self-understanding under constitutional law. Let me quote him at length:

“Constitutional patriotism,” it appears, is the morally necessitated readiness of a country's people to accept disagreement over the application of core constitutional principles of respect for everyone as free and equal, without loss of confidence in the univocal content of the principles, because and as long as they can understand the disagreement as strictly tied to struggles over constitutional identity. And what explains that readiness, when and where it is found? The answer to that must be that conditions then and there warrant a level of confidence that the struggle over corporate identity occurs within a corporate identity that is already incompletely, but *to a sufficient degree, known and fixed*.²⁹

As admittedly vital as it is, the notion of fixity frustrates the manner in which a post-national constitutional patriotism can move forward. It confirms a series of unresolved tensions in the application of Habermasian theory to the demands of post-national solidarity. This concern, in fact, goes to the heart of Habermas's discourse theory of law, since it complicates his main thesis about how law's procedural rationality holds together the crucial link between legality and legitimacy.³⁰

Responding adequately to this structural concern about constitutional fixity requires a shift in analytic frame: to that of the constitutional imaginary. The concept of constitutional imaginaries draws inspiration from social theoretical accounts of imaginaries, more broadly. These denote the symbolic collections of self-understandings—carried in images and stories and ways of thinking—that reflect crucial facts of social life and also normative expectations about how that social life ought to be lived.³¹ Derived foremost from the work of Cornelius Castoriadis, an imaginary ‘gives specific orientation to every institutional system, which overdetermines the choice and the connections of symbolic networks, which is the creation of each historical period, its singular manner of living, of seeing and of conducting its own existence, its world, and its relations with this world’.³²

Constitutional imaginaries, specifically, identify ideal-typical modes of legal thinking that structure both doctrinal thinking and broader civic commitments to the rule of law. These imaginaries include both utopian and ideological forces—‘the basis for articulating what does matter and what does not’.³³ And constitutional imaginaries thus open onto the law's normative ambitions while also constraining one's thinking about those ambitions. Imaginaries project our imagination but also ‘capture’ and restrain it, just in the way Ludwig Wittgenstein suggested: ‘A *picture* held us captive. And we could not get outside it, for it lay in our language and language seemed to repeat it to us inexorably’.³⁴

Using Hauke Brunkhorst's terminology, we can pose the difficulty posed by the analytic frame of constitutional imaginaries in the following way: within the democratic nation-state, constitutional law at once represents a revolutionary achievement of social solidarity insofar as law's normative force democratically orders systems integration; but it also undermines the spirit of this same achievement. For insofar as the constitution's positive law ‘fixes’ in place certain social understandings, future citizens subsequently encounter these not as the substrate of revolutionary possibilities but instead as evolutionary facts.³⁵ Efforts at novel forms of inclusion are at these points vulnerable to the defensive use of constitutional achievements as barriers to entry.

Constitutional imaginaries are the missing terrain of constitutional culture upon which Habermasian constitutional theory runs aground. Indeed, the tension between the utopian and the ideological in constitutional imaginaries holds one of the keys to a post-national, reflexive philosophy of law. Post-national solidarity, as a revolutionary reappraisal of the settled bonds of national solidarity, is thereby positioned precisely at the edge, at the fault line, of constitutional fixity. Fixity, like particularity, at once constitutes and prejudices the work of post-national solidarity. Any view of post-national constitutional patriotism must thereby inquire more deeply into to this negotiation of particularism and constitutional fixity. In the same way that a common political culture does indeed require a special mode of socialization, a post-national constitutional law requires its own ethical practices. That is to say, there must be something distinctive about a post-national constitutional culture that itself counteracts—or, more precisely, *changes the nature of*—the closure of constitutional fixity.

29 Frank Michelman, ‘Morality, Identity and “Constitutional Patriotism”’ (2001) 14(3) *Ratio Juris* 269, emphasis mine.

30 See Jürgen Habermas, ‘Law and Morality’ in *The Tanner Lectures on Human Values* (Salt Lake City 1990) vol 8, 217, 243-4.

31 See Charles Taylor, *Modern Social Imaginaries* (Durham: Duke University Press 2003).

32 Cornelius Castoriadis, *The Imaginary Institution of Society* (K Blamey trans, Cambridge: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 1987) 145.

33 *ibid.*

34 Ludwig Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations* (1958) ¶ 115.

35 See generally Hauke Brunkhorst, *Solidarity: From Civic Friendship to a Global Legal Community* (Cambridge, MA: Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 2005) 99-101.

IV. AT THE LIMITS OF PROCEDURAL THOUGHT

Habermas in his constitutional theory has responded to this difficulty by emphasizing the dynamic structure of agreement in legal procedures. Specifically, he appeals to the ‘all affected interests’ democratic principle of legitimacy: the foundational dictum that a polity must ‘not exclude anyone who is affected by the possible coercive measures of the legal community from the community of equal citizens’.³⁶ The democratic principle thereby combines a compositional standard of inclusion with a basic procedural mechanism for guiding political participation. It is at once a counter-factual ideal for assessing the legitimacy of laws and political decisions but also a deliberative model for how public institutions ought function.³⁷ The question is whether this procedural view is an adequate way to conceive post-national solidaristic legality and politics—to conceive the distinctive character of post-national constitutional culture.

Is it enough merely to track coercion—and to include those affected by that coercion in determinations of responsibility? What if the invocation of coercion depends, in fact, on a prior understanding of what coercion means, over which those who are to be included cannot have a say? This is the criticism made by Paulina Ochoa of Habermas’s understanding of dynamic constitutionalism.

The ‘all affected interests principle’, Ochoa writes, could indeed be a principle for democratic inclusion, but only when ‘individuals living on either side [of the boundary] could agree on an analysis and interpretation of the meaning of “having one’s interests affected by a decision”’.³⁸ In cases where such an agreement is not available *prior* to the decision for inclusion—as is the case with constitutionalism beyond the nation-state—reliance on the principle catches in a vicious circle. To deploy the ‘all affected interests principle’ means already to have made a preceding judgment about the nature and scope of the decision such that those affected individuals could be included in the decision-making process; however, these same individuals could not have themselves been involved in making this prior determination. The exercise would thus become one of ‘constitutional paternalism,’ as Ochoa terms it, where the appeal for inclusion is made by a group already established in power who cannot help but treat others unequally as they were not included in defining the terms of the very principles for their inclusion.³⁹

Ochoa reminds us how the universalistic principle of inclusion can be perceived by those who are asked to participate in its decision-making procedure as something constrained, partial, and inaccessible. And this perception is not mere confusion. It highlights a deeper dilemma in the relations underlying discursive procedures that, while aiming to realize equal recognition, nonetheless permit some to control the terms of an encounter, to set the terms of equality and of participation for others. Indeed, European public spheres today seem to find themselves in this sort of difficulty: the expansion of communicative exchange across boundaries of national political spheres does not in itself secure a transformative openness to those other modes of life. More must be said about the processes that are imagined to attend this expansion, lest what is secured remains merely a composite public sphere experienced by still-national citizens and still structured according to the dominant imaginaries of national sovereignty. Is this not analogous, for example, to the trap we confront in the reception of refugees, a form of conditional hospitality that *a priori* structures the encounter in the native host’s favour? As Jacques Derrida memorably argued, the stranger ‘must ask for hospitality in a language which by definition is not his own, the one imposed on him by the master of the house, the host, the king, the lord, the authorities’.⁴⁰ The real philosophical issue in the problem to which the principle of discourse (D) is applied—as Ochoa’s analysis seems to suggest—concerns how we are to understand the relationship between discourse, identity, and the ethical-cultural dimensions of solidarity.

And here emerges a second critique: the ‘all affected interests principle’—in the emptiness of its universalism—might in fact smuggle in an orientation toward sovereign action that is antithetical to post-national solidaristic relations. If the critique of proceduralism’s abstraction tracks the elision of lifeworld self-understandings, this second critique concerns the manner in which proceduralism returns citizens into social lives but with a distorted image of their agency. This aligns with what Patchen Markell has critiqued as the orientation toward mastery at the heart of the politics of recognition.⁴¹ Markell argues that efforts to secure recognition are flawed responses to the ‘experience of vulnerability, to the fact that to the fact that our identities are shaped in part through the unpredictable responses of other people’.⁴² This response threatens to unravel precisely one’s capacity to *remain* responsive to such vulnerability. The push of legal recognition here demands that ‘others recognize us as who we *already* really are’.⁴³

36 See *ibid* 170.

37 See Seyla Benhabib, ‘Toward a Deliberative Model of Democratic Legitimacy’ in S Benhabib (ed), *Democracy and Difference: Contesting the Boundaries of the Political* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 1996)

38 Paulina Ochoa, *The Time of Popular Sovereignty: Process and the Democratic State* (University Park: Pennsylvania State University Press 2011) 42.

39 *ibid*.

40 Jacques Derrida, *Of Hospitality* (R Bowlby tr, Stanford: Stanford University Press 2000) 15.

41 See generally Markell, *Bound by Recognition* (n 17) 12ff.

42 *ibid* 14.

43 *ibid*.

The retention of this underlying pursuit of sovereignty is most germane for the post-national concern with constitutional fixity. And it suggests why formal procedural openness is inadequate for thinking through post-national legal solidarity. In terms of its underlying civic orientation, constitutional fixity can be reformulated as the case when the legal system preserves this 'basic aspiration behind [sovereign] agency: the aspiration to be able to act independently, without experiencing life among others as a source of vulnerability, or as a site of possible alienation or self-loss'.⁴⁴ Post-national solidarity, then, aims to respond to a particular and fundamental kind of injustice this problem contains, aptly described in terms of an underlying structure of subordination. Drawing on WEB DuBois's analysis of whiteness, Markell writes that 'such structures pay an *ontological* wage: they organize the human world in ways that make it possible for certain people to enjoy an imperfect simulation of the invulnerability they desire, leaving others to bear a disproportionate share of the costs and burdens involved in social life'.⁴⁵

This critique is important to bear in mind. The discussion thus far has been at a very high level of abstraction, so consider for a moment a particular example from EU law: the legal framework of asylum and the changing character of solidarity within it. In the combined cases *NS and ME*, the European Court of Justice affirmed in 2011 that a Member State's discretion to refuse a transfer under the Dublin system in fact becomes an obligation in cases where rights of the applicant under Article 4 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights are in question and when 'they cannot be unaware that systemic deficiencies in the asylum procedure' in the receiving state.⁴⁶ Following the decision, the prohibition on transfers to states with 'systemically deficient' asylum protections was incorporated into the Dublin Regulation's recast, Dublin III.

Is this an adequate way to 'include' others and to respect their rights—thus better approximating the universal demands of justice in European constitutional law? From what we know of the developments of European asylum law, we can hardly be confident in an affirmative answer. If the prohibition on transfer in these circumstances is often viewed as an important first step, it nevertheless represents a rather passive and limited understanding of what solidarity demands. Consider here how, in requiring a refusal of transfer to states where 'systemic deficiencies' in asylum protections existed, Dublin III also sanctioned a kind of withdrawal, where responsibility of Member States to the rights of asylum seekers was understood in isolation, despite the transnational systemic entanglement of states and their (mutually implicated) factual capacities to respond to asylum claims. Relying on Dublin's 'sovereignty clause' and their own interpretations of the meaning of 'systemic deficiencies', Dublin III implicitly, though decisively, affirms a solipsistic ideological conceit privileging a national frame for responsibility under European refugee law.

This national frame can bear ambiguous results from the perspective of rights protection—some to heighten protection and others to reduce it. Earlier in the history of the AFSJ, for example, states in certain circumstances refused to recognize the asylum jurisdiction of fellow Member States—on the basis not of a new prospective legal agreement of humanitarian standards—but instead on account of their own criteria of refugee status and protection defined under national law. This was the approach of the UK Court of Appeals in 1999 when it denied transfer by the Home Office of asylum seekers to French and German jurisdiction on grounds that the latter's more restrictive policies failed to offer asylum, unlike the United Kingdom, on grounds of persecution by agents other than the state.⁴⁷ But this same national frame also bore fruit, as it did after *NS/ME*, in the discretionary reluctance to apply the 'systemic deficiencies' test to other states undergoing difficulties of adequately protecting refugee rights—and thus to keep 'trusting' their deficient asylum laws.⁴⁸

Under these auspices of mutual trust, European states have long avoided confronting the ways individual national legal cultures and particular practices developed—and the ways these developments affected one another. With regard to the Dublin Regulation's structure and its rule on the 'first country of entry', in particular, this permitted core states to ignore increased pressures on the national legal systems of states on the periphery, all the while continuing to formally abide by their rights obligations. More deeply still—as *NS/ME* and the Dublin III reform demonstrates—some states were thereafter permitted, in the guise of rebalancing the principle of mutual trust, to continue to 'set the terms' for others—whether peripheral states or asylum seekers themselves—of equality and participation in deciding where claims to asylum are to be processed.

44 *ibid* 12.

45 *ibid* 22.

46 Joined Cases C-411/10 and C-493/10, *NS v Secretary of State for the Home Department and ME and others v Refugee Applications Commissioner and Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform* [2011] ECR I-13905, para 98, 106.

47 *R v. SSHD, ex parte Adan, Subaskaran and Aitseguer*, 1999 INLR 472. See Sandra Lavenex, 'Mutual recognition and the monopoly of force: limits of the single market analogy' (2007) 14(5) *Journal of European Public Policy* 762-69, 772.

48 See Susan Fratzke, 'Not Adding Up: The Fading Promise of Europe's Dublin System' (Migration Policy Institute Europe 2015) 18 ('Despite increasing evidence of failings in Italy's asylum procedures, for example, most asylum authorities have been hesitant to use the logic of the CJEU's decision in *N.S./M.E.* to refrain from transferring claims to Italy. In Austria, asylum authorities have declined to do so on the grounds that, since the Commission has not instituted infringement procedures, Italy is still fulfilling its obligations under EU law. The ECtHR also found, in 2013, that returns to Italy were permissible in specific cases').

The lesson of this example is pressing. The procedural turn always threatens to deceive—to reinscribe narrow sovereign prerogative just as Markell suggests. While contemporary geopolitical and economic pressures do throw into question the sociological status of sovereignty understood as state capacity, the national state nonetheless continues to exercise extensive power in large part because it is able to ‘draw upon a history of relatively stabilized relations of recognition’.⁴⁹ These relations not only afford the state authority, Markell writes, but also enable it to ‘set the terms of exchanges of recognition, creating incentives for people to frame their claims about justice in ways that abet rather than undermine the project of state sovereignty’.⁵⁰ While inclusion in discursive practices certainly may produce substantial recognition of previously ignored persons or claims, it would thereby be too hasty to conclude that this secures a robust grounding for post-national solidarity. Indeed, the opposite may very well be the case: progress toward inclusion might instead continue to privilege—in ways remaining hidden and unaddressed—assumptions about the nature of identity and action (something over which one desires control) in a manner that in fact inhibits solidaristic affirmation of others.

Post-national solidarity demands something more: a differently imaginative mode of legal rationality and legal critique. The truly revolutionary post-national transformation is a change in orientation found not merely in formal-pragmatic discourses; it is an ethical-cultural change. The error of recognition occurs in the ethical-cultural presumptions that drive, beneath the surface, the distortions of the formal discursive principle.

V. THE PROBLEM OF LEGAL REASON’S EMPTY TIME

At theoretical fault here is a subtle shift in the level of analysis. Although Habermas often phrases the perspective of constitutional patriotism in quite personal terms, he nevertheless operates on a sociological level with the spectator, not the actor, in mind. Consider how he summarizes his own perspective on seeing the constitution as an ongoing project: ‘Thanks to the intuitive knowledge of what it means to frame a constitution, any citizen can put herself at any time in the shoes of a framer and check whether, and to what extent, the established practices and regulations of democratic deliberation and decision-making meet at present the required conditions for legitimacy-conferring procedures’.⁵¹ But in attributing to citizens the ability to skim across the surface of time, Habermas paints an implausible and, indeed, worrisome picture of a political community’s historical inheritance. It becomes frozen in time, able to be called forth in the same ways whenever one wishes. But, as Neeli Steele writes, ‘democratic subjects are not standing in a synchronic lifeworld together. Our inheritance does not simply stand in the background; it asks us questions, nourishes, and oppresses, and not in the same way for all members of a political community’.⁵² Founders and contemporaries can be ‘in the same boat’ only insofar as we ignore citizens as historical beings and we imagine moral constitutional principles to inhere in their logic, quite apart from their socially embedded rhetorical, political, and historical meanings.⁵³ The fixity of constitutional principles—the experience citizens have of their pull, which often prejudices the universal principles they otherwise seek to apply—is a matter of law’s time.

Habermas’s particular appeal to historical progress produces a rather consequential picture of citizens’ knowledge about their own identity and their expectations of it. It encourages a certain neglect of the degree of change and loss that marks the historical negotiation of constitutional principles and—just as importantly—the way such loss is distributed unevenly, with some bearing greater burden of it than others. It thereby retrenches the problem of constitutional fixity in the terms, drawing on Markell, I described above: the ‘basic aspiration behind [sovereign] agency: the aspiration to be able to act independently, without experiencing life among others as a source of vulnerability, or as a site of possible alienation or self-loss’.⁵⁴ This creates an empty vision of historical process—deprived of the genuine openings that come with affirming more radically the unpredictable nature of political encounters and, thereby, for considering how this unpredictability must affect constitutional principles themselves.

The problem, then, is not just that the historical progressive account becomes hegemonic over competing interpretations of historical possibility. A developmental view of historical progress also fails to acknowledge the importance of temporality for the relationship of the lifeworld to law and for the dynamic effects of constitutional imaginaries. The emphasis on procedural legal rationality subordinates ethical-cultural resources as secondary sites of motivational resources in part because it is less mindful of the fragility of culture, of the tentative manner in which cultural resources are produced over time and, indeed, how they can be lost—often precisely as they are rationalized in their contact with universalizing law. As Steele argues, Habermas’s view of practical reason seems to have little use for a phenomenological understanding of the lifeworld; the lifeworld is consequently an ‘empty, synchronic frame of common

49 *ibid* 30.

50 *ibid*.

51 Jürgen Habermas, ‘On Law and Disagreement: Some Comments on “Interpretative Pluralism”’ (2003) 16(2) *Ratio Juris* 187, 193. See also Jürgen Habermas, ‘Constitutional Democracy: A Paradoxical Union of Contradictory Principles?’ (2001) 29(6) *Political Theory* 766, 776ff.

52 Meili Steele, *Hiding from History: Politics and Public Imagination* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press 2005) 31.

53 See *ibid* 33.

54 *ibid* 12.

space' and 'not something that a political community can lose, gain, enrich, or impoverish'.⁵⁵

Disregarding the lifeworld's own temporality—and thus affording no space to analyze the symbolic and rhetorical work of constitutional imaginaries—undermines the difficult work of sustaining post-national solidarity. Affirming the scope of universalizing principles anew with regard to heretofore excluded groups requires reworking communal institutions and structures of meaning. Proceduralism moves too quickly and superficially over the delicate and fragile work this in fact entails. This oversight yields, among other things, unhelpful political dynamics. When citizens sense for themselves the cultural lifeworld's fragility and yet are constantly reassured rationalization will render it no less available, it should not surprise that in crucial moments many turn defensively to exaggerated populist visions of cultural community. Without a more careful assessment of how cultural resources relate constitutively to normative principles, little can shift the underlying investment of citizens in a problematic vision of identity as a ground of sovereign action, derived at the expense of others. Nihilism, demotivation, and its populist responses arise not because of critique alone; they come by virtue of a combination of critique and this continued cultural investment in a homogenizing, invulnerable view of identity.

VI. RECLAIMING TEMPORALITY IN LEGAL IMAGINATION

Habermas's 'learning sovereign' must begin to learn differently beneath the mantle of constitutional patriotism. What might define a more illuminating solution in this sense? The work of Seyla Benhabib provides a fruitful opening. Benhabib's calls for inclusion are no simple proceduralism that would overtake the capacities and meanings of lifeworld self-understandings. Instead, Benhabib emphasizes the hermeneutic work of narrative:

'Differences in perspective result from the different narrative histories in which selves are embedded. At any points in time, we are one whose identity is constituted by a tale. This tale is never complete: the past is always reformulated and renarrated in the light of the present and in anticipation of a future. Yet this tale is not one of which we alone are the authors. Others not only play a role in our tale but often tell our stories for us and make us aware of their real meaning. The self's identity is revealed only in such a community of interaction; who we are is how we reveal ourselves to others and to ourselves in such processes'.⁵⁶

The turn to narrative is an elegant reformulation. It opens a political community to reappraisal without simultaneously denying the grounds of its intelligible judgment of whatever new validity might be uncovered. Indeed, this is akin to G.H. Mead's reference to the 'larger community' of past and future, in contradistinction to Habermas's more abstract understanding of an idealized community of communication. As Jay Bernstein writes, '[Mead's] appeal is to *a future but not idealized continuation* of this community, to a transformed or transfigured extension of existing practices that would realize a potentiality in them denied by their existing configuration'.⁵⁷ The claim would not be a formal-pragmatic one but rather an expression of potentiality, of possibility. It would be formulated in view of a community's own sense of how 'they *both* are and could be, as they could be in response to how they are here and now'.⁵⁸

This entails affirming the historical point of view: a historical sensitivity that is integral to the horizon against which we reason and judge. We cannot make sense of normative claims without first situating them within the course of our past experience as it arcs across time into the future. But history and future narratives also have a second role, counter-intuitively related to the first. Historically conscious reasoning not only grounds judgment or makes it intelligible as our own; they introduce an element of play and creativity into what we understand 'our own' to mean. '[T]his tale is not one of which we alone are the authors'.⁵⁹ Read together with Mead, Benhabib's point makes one conscious of the movement of a polity in time, to its dislocation in time by action, such that one's identity is only ever legible as a retrospective judgment controlled not by actors themselves but by the 'tales' told by others.

The disclosure of identity's temporality has distinct emancipatory uses that make the decentering forms of post-national solidarity more possible, not less. History here is not a basis for firm knowledge of one's identity but an expression of identity's incompleteness; history enables us to see how the plurality and unpredictability of the world can still guide our ethical sense of ourselves. Indeed, it offers crucial rhetorical tools and discursive orientations for post-national solidarity. While invocations of identity speak to one's self-understanding, they need not remain 'fixated' by the desire for mastery or control.⁶⁰ Consequently, this means that a denial of one's fixed identity need not result in merely a deflating, *negative* reminder of our always incomplete imbrication in time. The narration of one's life in time does not necessarily

55 Steele, *Hiding from History* (n 52) 27.

56 Seyla Benhabib, *Critique, Norm, and Utopia: A Study of the Foundations of Critical Theory* (New York: Columbia University Press 1987) 349.

57 JM Bernstein, *Recovering Ethical Life: Jürgen Habermas and the Future of Critical Theory* (London and New York: Routledge 1995) 118, emphasis in original.

58 *ibid.*

59 Benhabib, *Critique, Norm, and Utopia* (n 56) 349.

60 Patchen Markell, *Bound by Recognition* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 2003) 186.

undermine the ground upon which we judge or act, due to its ever-shifting nature. As Markell notes, narration can perform a variety of re-constituting work that brings one closer to political action alongside others: ‘mourning, setting a scene, challenging or provoking, inviting ... [all the while] *not* playing at being sovereign’.⁶¹ These are instances of how facticity—the awareness and expression of one’s concrete position in the world—can be organized temporally in order to enable, rather than constrain, the ends of validity.

Constitutional law—due to its written form, its institutionalized exposition of normative commitments across time, its procedural guarantees, its calibration of rights and competences—is particularly well-positioned to attune a polity to such practices. But to understand how law performs this task, one must retain the category of constitutional culture and analyze how constitutional imaginaries influence politics in a post-national constitutional polity.

Consider in this light a revised role in constitutional patriotism of ‘memory’ and learning from the past. Max Pensky offers a magnificent reading of how ‘anamnesic solidarity’ might supplement modern, post-conventional forms of civic belonging.⁶² This entails not merely a duty ‘to remember,’ what Pablo de Greiff captures in the phrase: ‘we have an obligation to remember whatever our fellow citizens cannot be expected to forget’.⁶³ Anamnesic solidarity also entails a ‘deliberate and continuous effort to resist the imperative to construe past suffering as inhabiting a temporally safe and secure relationship with the present’.⁶⁴ This distinctive form of temporal learning brings together moral principles of inclusion with ethical processes of understanding our identity and its own genealogy—who we have come to be and who we might still wish to become. It thereby asks of political life an active responsibility. Unlike the cautious memory politics that remind a polity of catastrophe, this form of memory creates; it does not constrain. It prompts a ‘form of political motivation for resisting *ongoing* injustices that presumably would not have been possible’ without collective forgetting.⁶⁵ In my analysis, this is the task post-national constitutional patriotism would assign the institutions and processes of constitutional law. Law would serve as an institutional and semantic fulcrum: between past and future, between the acknowledgment of loss and the possibility of recovery.

In this modality of recovery, law—its structure and modes of interpretation—takes the form of a story, an ongoing narrative of popular sovereignty and democratic freedom in time. This narrative offers the objects and concerns for a post-national constitutional patriotism. But they are structured in a distinctive way as legal claims. In this register, law’s didactic character, as James Tully powerfully has considered, would be like that of an Aboriginal story, which ‘encourages and guides listeners to reflect independently on the great problems of life that he story presents to them through myths’.⁶⁶ The story does not cement the authority of a univocal claim to universal validity. On the contrary, in its authoritative standing it nevertheless remains pluralistic and open-ended. Tully writes eloquently of this form of validity: ‘The test of understanding a story is not the answer listeners might give in an exam, but how it affects their attitude and how they go on in various circumstances to conduct their life in light of what they have learned from reflection on the story. ... Because there is not one right answer or one truth to an allegory, it is possible to go on in a variety of ways and still be acting in accord with the story. There are a multitude of ways of being guided’.⁶⁷

This is not merely a giving and evaluation of reasons, not merely a practice of justification and testing of validity-claims. It is a process of active translation of ideas and values from one language to the next and back again.⁶⁸ This process neither validates some pre-existing claim nor expresses a direct conception of universality. Nor is it the simple reduction to the lowest common denominator of agreement. For this reason, its orientation cannot be one of defensive proceduralism. Rather, it looks to the *creation* of new insights to mutual recognition and understanding through a process of rooted, analogical reasoning across cases, traditions, and histories. It is this process that the notion of Mead’s ‘larger community’ and Pensky’s ‘anamnesic solidarity’ require.

61 *ibid.*

62 Max Pensky, ‘Solidarity with the Past and the Work of Translation: Reflections on Memory Politics and the Post-Secular’, draft available at <http://www.binghamton.edu/philosophy/people/docs/pensky-solidarity-translation.pdf>.

63 Pablo De Greiff, ‘The Duty to Remember: The Dead Weight of the Past, or the Weight of the Dead of the Past?’ unpublished, 18, cited in Pensky, ‘Solidarity with the Past and the Work of Translation’ (n 62) 22, emphasis omitted.

64 Pensky, ‘Solidarity with the Past and the Work of Translation’ (n 62) 31.

65 *ibid.*

66 James Tully, *Strange multiplicity: Constitutionalism in an age of diversity* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press 1995) 33.

67 *ibid.* Arash Abizadeh elaborates on a set of criteria to evaluate such forms of communication: ‘We can ask, for example, whether the interlocutors are open to *being* persuaded in addition to attempting to persuade. Or we can ask whether interlocutors have equal opportunities *over time* in different communicative contexts to participate in discourse, even if they cannot do so within *every* communicative context. Or we can ask whether participants in practical discourse have been given equal opportunities to develop their rhetorical, communicative skills as speakers and their capacity for critically evaluating communication as listeners’. Arash Abizadeh, ‘On the philosophy/rhetoric binaries, or, is Habermasian discourse motivationally impotent?’ (2007) 33(4) *Philosophy & Social Criticism* 445, 466.

68 Tully, *Strange multiplicity* (n 66) 133 (‘The dialogue in such constitutional negotiations usually consists in the back and forth exchange of speech acts of the form, “let me see if I understand what you said”, “let me rephrase what you said and see if you agree”, “Is what you said analogous to this example in my culture”, or “I am sorry, let me try another intermediate example that is closer”, or “can you acknowledge this analogy?” “Now I think I see what you are saying—let me put it this way for I now see that it complements my view”. The participants are gradually able to see the association from the points of view of each other and cobble together an acceptable intercultural language capable of accommodating the truth in each of their limited and complementary views and of setting aside the incompatible ones’)

Return for a moment to the context of mutual trust and European asylum law. We might conceive, in this paradigm of post-national legal narrative, an alternative form of judicial review of Dublin transfers—one of a different character than the mandated activation of the sovereignty clause as imagined in *NS/ME* and in Dublin III. This paradigm would speak the language of constitutional imaginaries: it would scrutinize how fellow jurisdictions implement principles and policy—as individuals engage in the concrete demands placed upon them by interwoven European asylum procedures. European asylum law here becomes much more than a set of normative expectations or, even, procedures with ‘systemic’ characteristics. Abiding by a principle of solidarity, the transfer state would in fact bear a burden to assess and, further, to aim to remedy the deficiencies in asylum procedures among recipient states. But this assessment cannot be understood as merely a license for withdrawal as a discretionary act of national sovereignty, as before. Precisely because it takes seriously the ideological self-deceptions of constitutional imaginaries, it cannot aim merely to compensate for prior deficiencies of an unjust framework it otherwise intends to retain fixed in place.

Solidarity’s story is more demanding than better inclusion into the existing set of affairs, in which national prerogatives remain relatively secure and stable. In triggering sovereign discretion, post-national solidarity also changes the expectations of who and what is sovereign in light of the interconnected causes of failure in the particular case. Sovereignty is here invoked not in the interest of defending national prerogatives in isolation, but to assess what the fundamental rights that activate the need for this discretion in fact demand as a matter of constitutional history and structure. This kind of responsiveness cannot reduce to formal criteria because it responds to conditions that are both inherited and always changing. These are conditions over which we cannot presume to exercise sovereign control.

Assessing whether a pending transfer abides by the fair sharing of responsibilities among states or does enough to protect rights of asylum seekers is predicated upon responsiveness to an unpredictable evolution of factual situations. These not only continually unsettle our confidence that fairness has been achieved but, more deeply and importantly, also our understanding of what fairness as a principle means and *might yet* mean. For this reason, in the context of ongoing reforms to the Dublin system, the appeal by Visegrad states for a highly discretionary mechanism of ‘flexible, effective solidarity’ is manifestly inadequate.⁶⁹ But unsatisfactory, too, are frameworks for emergency relocation measures, increased European financial contributions, and European Asylum Support Office assistance.⁷⁰ Both cases take far too granted the underlying distributions of state responsibility and think hardly at all about the need for new structural arrangements prompted by new interpretations of rights—interpretations that would reach to the heart of the EU’s carrier sanctions regime and requirements of its humanitarian visa obligations, to take two examples.⁷¹ A solidaristic approach cannot reduce merely to improving the ‘effectiveness’ of existing schemes of protection; it must also question the background presumptions about what ‘effective protection’ means as a legal and practical matter in the world.⁷²

VII. CONCLUSION: NARRATIVE AGENCY AND A POST-NATIONAL CONSTITUTIONAL IMAGINARY

The preceding analysis has been an exercise in critical constitutional thought. It has attempted to revive a post-national vision of Habermasian constitutional patriotism, more adequately speaking to the register of constitutional culture and constitutional imaginaries. In conjunction, it has explored a series of supporting ideas. The specific concepts emphasized above (ethical-cultural transformation, memory, anamnestic solidarity, possibility, responsiveness), each of these addresses the situation of the citizen and law *in time*. The need for post-national solidarity can be linked to the need for a new temporal paradigm of law: a new understanding of and sensitivity to the temporality of legal validity. Solidarity as a post-national legal principle is, above all, a temporal concept. And it holds together a new understanding of constitutional law beyond the nation-state.

In the appeal to temporality, I do not mean simply that that law has duration or that its politics can speed up or slow down. Rather, to understand the law in time is to note how it affords citizens a critical bearing to their polity’s past, present, and future and thus to an identity that is never fully formed. To the contrary, this bearing or attunement to time suggests to citizens the complex strands of historical and systemic entanglement that underlie any particular fixation of identity at present. Such attunement to time promises, in its own way, to redeem hopes of cosmopolitan justice. In his earlier work, Habermas was more sensitive to this temporal dimension and, with reference to the work of Walter Benjamin, the importance of reawakening those suppressed and unfulfilled expectations of the ever growing past.

⁶⁹ See *Solidarity and Responsibility in the CEAS*, Progress report by the Slovak Presidency, Council Doc. 15253/16.

⁷⁰ See Evangelia Tsourdi, ‘Solidarity at work? The prevalence of emergency-driven solidarity in the administrative governance of the Common European Asylum System’ (2017) 24(5) *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 667-686.

⁷¹ Consider, here, the evaluation of AG Mengozzi concerning the provision of humanitarian visas. Opinion of Advocate General Mengozzi, Case C-638/16 PPU, X and X v État belge [2017] ECLI:EU:C:2017:93.

⁷² For further elaboration of this line of argument, see Paul Linden-Retek, ‘The refugees we are: Solidarity, asylum, and critique in the European constitutional imagination’, *German Law Journal*, forthcoming.

Habermas writes in *The Philosophical Discourse of Modernity*: “To all past epochs [Benjamin] ascribes a horizon of unfulfilled expectations, and to the future-oriented present he assigns the task of experiencing a corresponding past through remembering, in such a way that we can fulfill its expectations with our weak messianic power”.⁷³

Relying on the work of history and memory, post-national constitutional law traces the form of a critical *narrative*, a reflexive account of transformative over time. At stake here, very much in the tradition of civic republican theory, is the creative judgment of citizens who, with Arendt, have the capacity to begin anew. But this beginning of course never comes from nowhere, and the revolutionary spirit is, instead, one that can awaken what a political community has previously forgotten, erased, or lost. When pressed to change by those beyond our drawn borders, we must struggle not only to hear their voices, but also to note the traces of past wrongs that have occasioned their cries. Critical scrutiny of these past wrongs—and their relevance for the enduring systemic conditions in which present injustices arise—is not possible through any straightforward appeal to procedural or formal-pragmatic principles. It is richer and more complex than that. It is a reflection of a responsive and responsible constitutional culture that creates the resources within itself to live on differently. It is attached, in the end, to the potential of learning itself and the open-ended thought—at heart post-national—of what kind of people we might yet become.

73 Jürgen Habermas, *The Philosophical Discourse of Modernity* (F Lawrence trans, Cambridge, MA: The Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press 1987) 14.

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